

CMIP6-based analysis of precipitation and temperature trends and their implications on water resource management in the Gidabo Watershed, Ethiopia

Degefu Dogiso

Agricultural Engineering Department, Institute of Technology, Hawassa University, P.O. Box 05, Hawassa, Ethiopia

*Corresponding author. E-mail: degefu.dd@gmail.com

 DD, 0009-0003-0285-8844; AM, 0009-0002-7192-7965; AK, 0000-0001-5986-6245

ABSTRACT

Climate change increasingly threatens water resources, particularly in climate-sensitive regions such as Ethiopia's Gidabo watershed. This study analyzed historical (1995–2014) and future (2021–2040 and 2041–2060) climate trends using an ensemble of six bias-corrected CMIP6 global climate models under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios. The non-parametric Mann–Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator were applied to detect trends in precipitation and temperature. The results show that precipitation exhibits slightly increasing but statistically non-significant trends, with mean rainfall projected to decline by up to 18.2% during the wet season, indicating greater variability and a shift toward drier conditions. Conversely, both maximum and minimum temperatures show significant upward trends across all seasons and scenarios. The mean annual minimum temperature is projected to increase from 12.01 °C in the baseline to 15.63 °C by mid-century under SSP5-8.5, a rise of +3.62 °C (≈30%). These changes suggest hotter, more evaporative, and water-stressed conditions that could intensify agricultural droughts and ecosystem stress. The findings highlight the need to integrate CMIP6-based projections into climate-resilient water allocation, irrigation planning, and watershed management to ensure sustainable resource use in the Gidabo watershed and similar East African regions.

Key words: climate trend, CMIP6 ensemble, Gidabo watershed, precipitation, temperature, water resource management

HIGHLIGHTS

- CMIP6 models project rising temperatures and variable precipitation in the Gidabo watershed.
- Minimum temperature increases are more significant than maximum temperatures.
- Wet season precipitation is projected to decline by up to 18.2%.
- Climate trends imply serious risks for water availability and agriculture.
- Findings support climate-resilient planning and adaptation strategies.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is one of the most pressing challenges facing humanity worldwide, manifesting through rising temperatures and changing weather patterns that affect ecosystems, economies, and societies (IPCC 2021; Usman *et al.* 2024). While its impacts vary geographically, some regions experience more pronounced effects than others (EPA 2024). Globally, land areas have generally become warmer and slightly wetter, with subtropical and mid-latitude regions experiencing the greatest warming (Alizadeh 2023). Although temperature variability has remained relatively stable, precipitation variability has increased, particularly in the tropics, raising the risk of droughts and floods. Future projections suggest wetter conditions in the Northern Hemisphere and more intense wet extremes in the Southern Hemisphere, reflecting a shift toward abnormal warm-wet or warm-dry conditions (Zhan *et al.* 2020; Dimri *et al.* 2021).

In East Africa, climate projections indicate that annual precipitation could increase by up to 35% in Ethiopia, Uganda, and Kenya, whereas some areas of southern Tanzania may experience declines (Gebrechorkos *et al.* 2023). Temperature increases of 2–6 °C are anticipated under high-emission scenarios, with near-term projections suggesting a 2 °C rise by mid-century, surpassing the global average (Dufatanye Umwali *et al.* 2024). These changes may exacerbate heat stress in low-lying areas and increase the frequency of extreme rainfall events, heightening flood risks (Gebrechorkos *et al.* 2023).

Within Ethiopia, climate trends exhibit complex spatial and temporal patterns. Annual and Kiremt (main rainy season) rainfall generally show increasing trends, while Belg (small rainy season) rainfall tends to decrease (Moges & Bhat 2021; Gashaw *et al.* 2023). Temperature trends indicate a significant rise, particularly in lowland eco-regions, accompanied by

high inter-annual and inter-seasonal variability (Gedefaw 2023). Future projections suggest continued warming and increased annual rainfall, although Belg rainfall may decline further (Moges & Bhat 2021).

Traditionally, the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) has relied on a 30-year climate normal (1981–2010) for climate assessment. However, this approach has limitations: it assumes a stabilized climate, averages out extreme events, and may underrepresent growing variability and hazards (Brázdil *et al.* 2022). Consequently, the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) adopts a 20-year baseline (1995–2014) and presents projections for the near-future (2021–2040) and mid-future (2041–2060) periods under different emission scenarios (IPCC 2021; Palmer *et al.* 2023).

Understanding climate trends in the Gidabo watershed is critical for adaptation and mitigation planning. Previous studies report rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns, with CORDEX-Africa projections indicating higher temperatures, increased evaporation, and shifted rainfall distributions (Alehu *et al.* 2021; Aragaw *et al.* 2023). However, the most recent CMIP6 projections have not been fully assessed in this region, leaving a gap in knowledge regarding future climate extremes and their implications for water resources.

This study addresses these gaps by analyzing CMIP6-based climate trends, focusing on precipitation and temperature under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios. Using an ensemble of six GCMs, we evaluate the baseline (1995–2014), near-future (2021–2040), and mid-future (2041–2060) periods to provide insights for sustainable water resource management in the Gidabo watershed in response to climate change. This study is among the first to integrate bias-corrected CMIP6 ensemble projections with water resource-oriented interpretation for the Gidabo watershed, offering a more management-focused perspective compared with previous purely climatic analyses.

2. METHODS

2.1. Description of the study area

The Gidabo River flows through the Gidabo watershed located in Ethiopia's Rift Valley Lakes Basin, finally flowing into Lake Abaya, the largest lake in the basin (Mechal *et al.* 2015). This watershed extends from the Soka Sonicho Mountains in the northwest (latitudes 6.11–6.58°N, longitudes 38.0–38.38°E), with elevations ranging between 3,178 and 1,171 m (Figure 1).

Figure 1 | Map of the Gidabo watershed.

Furthermore, the area undergoes four distinct rainfall phases: the primary wet season (April–May), the intermediate rainy period (September–October), a shorter rainy season (July–August), and a dry spell (November–February), with an annual rainfall average of 1,385 mm (Belihu *et al.* 2018). The watershed's soil is categorized into seven primary types, with Chromic Vertisols (28.18%), Lithosols (25.08%), and Chromic Luvisols (23.58%) being the most common, followed by Orthic Luvisols (10.03%), Chromic Cambisols (8.97%), Eutric Nitisols (3.72%), and Dystric Cambisols (0.10%) (Alehu *et al.* 2021).

2.2. Data collection

Observed data: Daily precipitation and temperature data (1985–2018) were collected from six meteorological stations: Bilate, Dila, Haysawita, Hagerselam, Yirgalem, and Aleta Wondo (Table 1).

Meteorological station contribution: Thiessen polygons were used to weight the contribution of each station based on the size of its polygon relative to the watershed area (Figure 2). This method provides computational efficiency and accurate spatial precipitation representation. Thiessen polygons were selected for their simplicity, computational efficiency, and adaptability in spatial interpolation. They define areas based on proximity to station edges, reducing computational demands. Additionally, they are effective in hydrologic modeling, providing accurate station weights and minimizing long-term bias in precipitation distribution, making them a practical choice for watershed studies (Li *et al.* 2020).

Climate model data: Six CMIP6 global climate models (GCMs) from the CMIP6 archive <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu#!/home> were downloaded. Six CMIP6 GCMs (Table 1) were selected based on several criteria: (i) demonstrated skill in reproducing historical precipitation and temperature patterns in East Africa and Ethiopia (Alaminie *et al.* 2021; Selamawit *et al.* 2022), (ii) availability of daily precipitation and temperature outputs for both historical (1995–2014) and future (2021–2060) periods under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios, (iii) representation of different model families and climate sensitivities to reduce structural uncertainty, and (iv) relatively fine spatial resolution compared with other CMIP6 models, improving reliability for regional-scale assessments.

2.3. Climate data processing and evaluation

2.3.1. Observed data preparation

Homogeneity checks were applied, and missing values were filled using inverse distance weighting (IDW). It is useful for spatially interpolating precipitation and temperature (Barbulescu *et al.* 2020).

Table 1 | List of selected CMIP6 GCMs and meteorological stations

GCMs' Data

S/N	GCM	Country	Resolution (Lat × Long)	No. of data availability years
1	CNRM-CM6-1	France	0.9 × 0.9	1995–2014 and 2021–2060
2	CNRM-ESM2-1	France	1.0 × 1.0	1995–2014 and 2021–2060
3	EC-Earth3-CC	Europe	0.7 × 0.7	1995–2014 and 2021–2060
4	MIROC6	Japan	1.4 × 1.4	1995–2014 and 2021–2060
5	MRI-ESM2-0	Japan	0.9 × 0.9	1995–2014 and 2021–2060
6	ACCESS-CM2	Australia	1.25 × 1.875	1995–2014 and 2021–2060

Metrological stations and data availability years

S/N	Stations	Longitude (°)	Latitude (°)	Altitude (m)	No. of data availability years
1	Yirgalem	38.43	6.75	1,786	34
2	Haysawita	38.57	6.90	2,240	34
3	Dila	38.30	6.37	1,579	34
4	Hagerselam	38.52	6.49	2,840	34
5	Bilate	38.04	6.45	1,550	34
6	Aleta Wondo	38.42	6.60	1,947	34

Figure 2 | Thiessen Polygon map of the Gidabo watershed: Contribution percentages of six meteorological stations.

2.3.2. Regridding of GCM outputs

To ensure compatibility with the spatial extent of the study watershed, GCM outputs were re-gridded to $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ using bilinear interpolation in Python 3.12.4.

2.3.3. Bias correction of GCM outputs

The distribution mapping (DM) method in CMhyd software corrected systematic biases in temperature and precipitation by aligning cumulative distribution functions of model and observed data. This method preserves extreme values and is suitable across climate scenarios (Daniel 2023). Moreover, it preserves climate signals, improves the modeling of extreme values, and is flexible across different climate scenarios (Passow & Donner 2020). In addition, the method was previously applied in the study watershed and found to be effective (Woldesembet *et al.* 2022). The CMhyd provides bias correction using non-parametric, ensemble, and customized approaches for efficient climate data adjustment (Rathjens *et al.* 2016).

2.3.4. Validation of the bias-corrected data

To evaluate the accuracy of the bias-corrected data, the study employed five statistical metrics: the correlation coefficient (r) to measure the linear relationship, Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) for assessing model performance, the coefficient of determination (R^2) for explaining variance, root mean square error (RMSE) for evaluating model prediction accuracy, and percent bias (PBIAS) for assessing model bias.

2.3.5. Statistical evaluation of GCM performance

GCM performance was assessed using the downscaled climate data were evaluated with observed data using five common statistical parameters. These are NSE, r , R^2 , PBIAS, and RMSE.

(i) *Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE)*: Measures how well-simulated data matches observed data. Ranges from $-\infty$ to 1, with 1 indicating perfect prediction, >0.5 generally good, and <0 worse than the mean of observed values

(Moriassi *et al.* 2007).

$$\text{NSE} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - S_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad (1)$$

(ii) *Root mean squared error (RMSE)*: The square root of MSE, providing error in the same units as the data. Easier to interpret than MSE, with lower RMSE indicating better model performance.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - S_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

(iii) *Percent bias (PBIAS)*: Measures the average tendency of the model to over- or under-predict observed values, expressed as a percentage. PBIAS = 0 indicates a perfect match; positive values indicate overestimation, while negative values indicate underestimation.

$$\text{PBIAS} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - O_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n O_i} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

(iv) *Coefficient of determination (R^2)*: Measures the proportion of variance in observed data explained by the model, ranging from 0 to 1. Higher values (closer to 1) indicate a strong linear relationship between observed and simulated data, though it does not account for bias or error magnitude.

$$R^2 = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})(S_i - \bar{S})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - \bar{S})^2}} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where O_i is the observed value at time i , S_i is the simulated value at time i , \bar{O} is the mean of observed values, n is the number of observations, and \bar{S} is the mean of simulated values.

2.4. Trend analysis

2.4.1. Overview of the Mann-Kendall method

The MK test is a common non-parametric statistical method for identifying trends in time series data, especially in climate and environmental research. It determines whether there is a monotonic upward or downward trend without requiring the data to confirm a specific distribution (Mann 1945; Kendall 1975).

The MK trend test was used in this study to investigate trends in the climatic variable, precipitation, considered. The test was based on S statistics, and each pair of observed values x_j ($j > k$) of the random variable was inspected to find out whether $x_j > x_k$ or $x_j < x_k$.

The Mann-Kendall S Statistic is computed as follows:

$$S = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) \quad (5)$$

where x_j and x_k are the annual values in years j and k , $j > k$, respectively, and n is the length of the dataset. If the value of S is positive, there is an upward trend, and vice versa.

$$\text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x_j - x_k > 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } x_j - x_k = 0 \\ -1, & \text{if } x_j - x_k < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The variance of S is

$$\text{VAR}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{18} \quad (7)$$

The statistic S is approximately normal distributed provided that the following Z transformation is employed:

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{\sigma}}, & \text{if } S > 0 \\ \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{\sigma}}, & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{\sigma}}, & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The presence of a statistically significant trend was evaluated using the Z value. A positive and negative value of Z indicates an upward (downward) trend. The statistic Z has a normal distribution. To test for either an upward or downward monotonic trend (a two-tailed test) at α 95% level of significance, H_0 is rejected if the absolute value of Z is greater than $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$, where $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ is obtained from the standard normal cumulative distribution tables. For this study, the confidence level of 95% was determined by the test statistics.

Theil-Sen estimator: The Theil-Sen estimator for the slope m is calculated as follows:

Pairwise slopes: For each pair of observations (x_i, y_i) and (x_j, y_j) where $i < j$, compute the slope m_{ij} using the formula:

$$m_{ij} = \frac{y_j - y_i}{x_j - x_i} \quad (9)$$

This slope is computed for all pairs of points in the dataset.

The median of slopes: The Theil-Sen estimator for the slope m is then the median of all the computed pairwise slopes:

$$m = \text{median}[m_{ij}] \quad (10)$$

Kendall's tau: The formula for Kendall's tau is given by

$$\tau = \frac{(C - D)}{\frac{1}{2}n(n-1)} \quad (11)$$

where C is the number of concordant pairs, D is the number of discordant pairs, and n is the number of observations.

2.5. Mean shift computation

Changes between baseline (1995–2014) and future periods (2021–2060) were quantified as

$$\text{Absolute Mean Shift} = \mu_{\text{future}} - \mu_{\text{baseline}} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Relative (Percentage)Shift} = \left(\frac{\mu_{\text{future}} - \mu_{\text{baseline}}}{\mu_{\text{baseline}}} \right) \times 100 \quad (13)$$

where μ_{future} and μ_{baseline} are the means of the baseline and future periods.

2.6. Scenario design

The analysis considered three time periods: baseline (1995–2014), near-future (2021–2040), and mid-century (2041–2060), following CMIP6 model availability. Based on local climatic conditions (Ware *et al.* 2023), the wet season was defined as March–September and the dry season as October–February.

Trends in precipitation and temperature were evaluated for annual, wet, and dry seasons using the Mann–Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator. The absolute (ΔX) and relative (%) mean shifts between baseline and future periods were also calculated to quantify change magnitude under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios.

2.7. Schematic representation of the methodology of the study

The methodology of this study, from data collection to analysis, as well as result interpretation, is presented in Figure 3.

3. RESULTS

3.1. GCM output validation

The statistical evaluation of six CMIP6 GCMs and their ensemble mean using the CMhyd bias correction method reveals strong performance in simulating both precipitation (PCP) and temperature (TMP). The correlation coefficients (CORELL) for all models are high, ranging from 0.90 to 0.99, indicating strong linear agreement with observed data. RMSE values for PCP are between 0.03 and 0.06, while TMP RMSE ranges from 0.054 to 0.125, with ACCESS-CM2 showing the highest TMP RMSE. The PBIAS for PCP ranges from -2.01 (MIROC6) to 5.74 (EC-Earth3-CC), whereas TMP PBIAS values are all negative, indicating slight underestimation. NSE values are consistently high across models, ranging from 0.74 to 0.98 for PCP and 0.80 to 0.98 for TMP, showing good model efficiency. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is similarly strong, with values between 0.81 and 0.99 for both variables. The ensemble mean generally improves model reliability,

Figure 3 | The general methodological flow of the study.

showing balanced statistics (e.g., CORELL = 0.98–0.99, NSE = 0.78–0.95), making it a robust option for climate impact studies.

Taylor diagrams show that climate models perform better for temperature than for precipitation, with higher correlations and lower deviations. EC-Earth3-CC and CNRM-ESM2-1 best capture precipitation patterns, while temperature models align closely with observations. The ensemble mean outperforms individual models, enhancing accuracy (Figure 4).

3.2. Precipitation trends in the watershed

3.2.1. Baseline period (1995–2014)

An increasing but statistically non-significant trend in precipitation was observed for the annual, wet, and dry seasons, with corresponding Z-scores of -1.33 , -0.876 , and -1.006 , respectively (Table 2).

Figure 4 | Taylor diagram showing the performance of GCMs compared with observed data: (a) precipitation and (b) temperature.

Table 2 | Statistical evaluation of precipitation and temperature trends

Different periods and scenarios		Statistical parameters									
Periods	Scenarios	Z-score			Kendall's tau			Sen's slope			
		PCP	TMP max	TMP min	PCP	TMP max	TMP min	PCP	TMP max	TMP min	
Baseline	Annual (1995–2014)	-1.330	2.044*	3.407*	-0.221	0.337	0.558	-10.012	0.025	0.074	
	Wet season (1995–2014)	-0.876	1.784	3.666*	-0.147	0.295	0.600	-5.974	0.026	0.082	
	Dry season (1995–2014)	-1.006	1.006	2.823*	-0.168	0.168	0.463	-2.523	0.016	0.061	
Future	Annual	SSP2-4.5 (2021–2040)	0.162	2.758*	4.185*	0.032	0.453	0.684	0.802	0.027	0.073
		SSP2-4.5 (2041–2060)	0.876	3.082*	4.445*	0.147	0.505	0.726	6.015	0.035	0.074
		SSP5-8.5 (2021–2040)	0.097	3.277*	3.991*	0.021	0.537	0.653	0.199	0.039	0.076
	Wet season	SSP5-8.5 (2041–2060)	1.590	3.472*	4.704*	0.263	0.568	0.768	5.700	0.042	0.097
		SSP2-4.5 (2021–2040)	-0.876	3.017*	4.380*	-0.147	0.495	0.716	-2.426	0.046	0.084
		SSP2-4.5 (2041–2060)	0.616	3.017*	4.250*	0.105	0.495	0.695	2.389	0.046	0.079
	Dry season	SSP5-8.5 (2021–2040)	-1.071	2.888*	3.991*	-0.179	0.474	0.653	-3.396	0.053	0.086
		SSP5-8.5 (2041–2060)	1.071	3.407*	4.640*	0.179	0.558	0.758	2.979	0.043	0.105
		SSP2-4.5 (2021–2040)	1.200	0.811	3.601*	0.200	0.137	0.589	2.730	0.008	0.055
		0.681	1.914	3.796*	0.116	0.316	0.621	1.336	0.031	0.062	
		1.265	2.109*	3.017*	0.211	0.347	0.495	2.524	0.030	0.065	
		1.784	1.914	4.769*	0.295	0.316	0.779	3.866	0.038	0.083	

PCP, precipitation; TMP max, maximum temperature; TMP min, minimum temperature.

*Shows a significant trend.

3.2.2. Future period (2021–2060)

3.2.2.1. Near-future period (2021–2040). Under the SSP2-4.5 scenario, precipitation exhibited a non-significant increasing trend during both the annual and wet seasons, whereas the dry season showed a non-significant decreasing trend, with corresponding Z-scores of 0.162, 1.2, and -0.876 , respectively. Similarly, under the SSP5-8.5 scenario, a statistically non-significant increasing trend was observed in the annual and wet seasons; however, the dry season experienced a non-significant decreasing trend, with Z-scores of 0.097, 1.265, and -0.071 , respectively (Table 2).

3.2.2.2. Mid-future period (2041–2060). Under the SSP2-4.5 scenario, precipitation showed a statistically non-significant increasing trend across the annual, wet, and dry seasons, with corresponding Z-scores of 0.076, 0.616, and 0.68, respectively. Likewise, under the SSP5-8.5 scenario, a statistically non-significant increasing trend was observed in all three seasons, with Z-scores of 1.6, 1.07, and 1.78, respectively (Figure 5 and Table 2).

3.3. Temperature trends

3.3.1. Mean maximum temperature

3.3.1.1. Baseline period. Under the baseline scenario, maximum temperature showed a statistically significant increasing trend in the annual and non-significant increasing trends in the wet and dry seasons, with corresponding Z-scores of 2.044, 1.78, and 1.006, respectively (Table 2).

3.3.1.2. Future period. Near-future period

Under the SSP2-4.5 scenario, maximum temperature exhibited a statistically significant increasing trend during the annual and wet seasons, while the dry season showed a non-significant increasing trend, with corresponding Z-scores of 2.75, 3.017, and 0.811, respectively. In contrast, under the SSP5-8.5 scenario, maximum temperature showed a statistically significant increasing trend across all three seasons: annual, wet, and dry with Z-scores of 3.27, 2.88, and 2.109, respectively (Table 2).

Mid-future period

Under the SSP2-4.5 scenario, maximum temperature showed a statistically significant increasing trend in both the annual and wet seasons, while the dry season exhibited a non-significant increasing trend, with corresponding Z-scores of 3.08, 3.4, and 1.9, respectively. Similarly, under the SSP5-8.5 scenario, a statistically significant increasing trend was observed in the annual and wet seasons, whereas the dry season showed a non-significant increasing trend, with Z-scores of 3.47, 3.4, and 1.9, respectively (Table 2 and Figure 6).

3.3.2. Mean minimum temperature

3.3.2.1. Baseline period. Under the baseline scenario, minimum temperature showed a statistically significant increasing trend in the annual, wet, and dry seasons, with corresponding Z-scores of 3.4, 3.6, and 2.8, respectively (Table 2).

3.3.2.2. Future period. Near-future period

Under the SSP2-4.5 scenario, minimum temperature exhibited a statistically significant increasing trend across the annual, wet, and dry seasons, with corresponding Z-scores of 4.18, 4.38, and 3.6, respectively. Likewise, under the SSP5-8.5 scenario, a statistically significant increasing trend was observed in all three seasons, with Z-scores of 3.9, 3, and 3.01, respectively (Table 2).

Mid-future period

Under the SSP2-4.5 scenario, minimum temperature exhibited a statistically significant increasing trend across the annual, wet, and dry seasons, with Z-scores of 4.44, 4.25, and 3.80, respectively. Similarly, under the SSP5-8.5 scenario, a statistically significant increasing trend was observed in all three seasons, with corresponding Z-scores of 4.70, 4.60, and 4.70, respectively (Table 2 and Figure 7).

3.4. Mean change between baseline and future periods

3.4.1. Precipitation mean change

Under both SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios, precipitation is projected to decline in the annual and wet seasons, with mixed patterns in the dry season. Compared with the 1995–2014 baseline, annual precipitation under SSP2-4.5 is expected to decrease by about 12.6% in both near (2021–2040) and mid-century (2041–2060) periods, while wet season precipitation

Figure 5 | Annual, wet and dry season precipitation trends.

declines by 15.6 and 18.2%. The dry season shows a slight decrease near-term and a small increase mid-century. Under SSP5-8.5, annual precipitation decreases by 12.1% near-term and 7.6% mid-century, with similar wet season declines and a slight dry season increase by mid-century (Table 3).

Figure 6 | Mean annual, wet and dry season maximum temperature trends.

Figure 7 | Annual, wet and dry seasons minimum temperature trends.

Table 3 | Mean change evaluation of precipitation and temperature

Scenarios	Mean change analysis for precipitation, maximum, and minimum temperature																	
	Annual						Wet season						Dry season					
	PCP	Δ (%)	TMP max	Δ (%)	TMP min	Δ (%)	PCP	Δ (%)	TMP max	Δ (%)	TMP min	Δ (%)	PCP	Δ (%)	TMP max	Δ (%)	TMP min	Δ (%)
Baseline (1995–2014)	1,201.12	0.00	28.17	0	12.01	0	884.01	0.00	27.37	0	12.14	0	317.12	0.00	29.31	0	11.82	0
SSP2-4.5 (2021–2040)	1,049.65	−12.6	29.81	5.82	13.46	12.07	746.15	−15.6	28.03	2.40	13.80	13.67	303.50	−4.3	29.92	2.08	12.97	9.73
SSP2-4.5 (2041–2060)	1,049.91	−12.6	29.57	4.97	14.77	22.98	723.32	−18.18	28.88	5.52	15.28	25.86	326.58	2.98	30.56	4.26	14.05	18.87
SSP5-8.5 (2021–2040)	1,055.38	−12.13	29.92	6.21	13.69	22.98	739.20	−16.4	28.18	2.96	14.06	15.82	316.18	−0.3	29.99	2.32	13.18	11.51
SSP5-8.5 (2041–2060)	1,110.15	−7.6	29.91	6.18	15.63	30.14	768.74	−13	29.26	6.91	16.27	34.02	341.41	7.66	30.84	5.22	14.73	24.62

PCP, precipitation in mm; Δ, relative change; TMP max, maximum temperature in °C; TMP min, minimum temperature in °C.

3.4.2. Maximum temperature mean change

Unlike precipitation, maximum temperature shows a consistent rise across all seasons and scenarios. Under SSP2-4.5, the annual mean maximum temperature is projected to increase by 1.64 °C (5.82%) in the near-term (2021–2040) and 1.42 °C (4.97%) in the mid-century period (2041–2060), relative to the baseline (28.17 °C). Seasonal analysis indicates that the wet season experiences higher increases (1.46 and 1.51 °C) than the dry season (0.88 and 0.97 °C).

Under SSP5-8.5, the annual mean maximum temperature is projected to rise by 1.75 °C (6.21%) and 1.80 °C (6.18%) for the near and mid-century periods, respectively, with the wet season again showing larger gains (1.55 and 1.69 °C) than the dry season (0.86 and 0.91 °C) (Table 3).

3.4.3. Minimum temperature mean change

Minimum temperature exhibits the most substantial warming. Under SSP2-4.5, the annual mean minimum temperature increases by 1.45 °C (12.07%) in the near-term and 2.76 °C (22.98%) in the mid-century period, relative to the baseline (12.01 °C). The wet season shows larger rises (1.46 and 2.89 °C) compared with the dry season (1.16 and 2.23 °C).

Similarly, under SSP5-8.5, annual minimum temperature increases by 2.76 °C (22.98%) and 3.62 °C (30.14%) for the near and mid-century periods, respectively. The wet season records the greatest warming (1.65 and 3.51 °C), exceeding that of the dry season (1.65 and 2.91 °C).

This pronounced increase in minimum temperature aligns with the projected decline in annual and wet season precipitation, particularly under the high-emission scenario, suggesting enhanced warming and potential evapotranspiration stress across the watershed (Table 3).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Evaluation of GCM performance for temperature and precipitation

The higher performance of GCMs in simulating temperature compared with precipitation can be explained by the relatively smoother spatial and temporal patterns of temperature, which are more readily captured by GCMs. In contrast, precipitation is characterized by considerable spatial variability and is strongly influenced by localized convective processes and topographic effects, resulting in greater uncertainty in model simulations. These observations are consistent with previous studies (Dubache *et al.* 2021; Lebeza *et al.* 2024).

4.2. Precipitation trends

Historical precipitation analysis in the Gidabo watershed indicates slight but statistically non-significant increasing trends in annual, wet, and dry seasons, with *Z*-scores of -1.33 , -0.876 , and -1.006 , respectively. Similar findings from other Ethiopian watersheds reveal spatial and temporal variability: for example, Ziway Lake and Modjo catchments show mostly insignificant rainfall trends, while the Tana sub-basin exhibits small, non-significant increases (Dadi *et al.* 2024). These patterns emphasize the need for ongoing monitoring and adaptive water management under climate uncertainty.

Near-future projections (2021–2040) for Gidabo under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 also suggest slight, non-significant increases in annual and wet season rainfall, with minor declines in the dry season. Comparable trends are reported in other Ethiopian regions, including increased rainfall in Kessem and the Omo Basin, alongside national tendencies toward fewer wet spells, more dry spells, and intensified extreme rainfall events (Assfaw *et al.* 2023; Feyissa *et al.* 2024). These signals indicate shifting seasonal rainfall patterns that may impact water availability and drought risk.

For the mid-future period (2041–2060), Gidabo's precipitation projections under both scenarios continue to show non-significant but consistent increasing trends across all seasons, with *Z*-scores ranging from 0.076 to 1.78. This aligns with regional studies forecasting moderate rainfall increases in Ethiopia's watersheds (Abebe *et al.* 2022), reinforcing the need for cautious interpretation and sustained climate monitoring.

4.3. Mean maximum temperature trends

The Gidabo watershed shows a statistically significant increase in annual maximum temperature, with positive but non-significant upward trends during wet and dry seasons. This pattern aligns with regional warming trends in East Africa, where maximum temperatures have risen by up to 1.9 °C, and similar increases are reported in Zambia, Malawi, and South Africa (Demissie & Gebrechorkos 2024).

Climate projections under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios suggest continued maximum temperature increases in the watershed, with stronger warming under SSP5-8.5. These projections correspond with CMIP6 estimates of 2.4–4.4 °C rises in East Africa by 2100 (Ayugi *et al.* 2021) and similar basin-level findings in Ethiopia (Alaminie *et al.* 2021). Overall, the upward trend in maximum temperature highlights increasing heat stress risks and underscores the importance of incorporating these projections into regional adaptation planning.

4.4. Minimum temperature trends

Recent studies show significant warming across East Africa and Ethiopia, with maximum temperatures rising to 1.9 °C and minimum temperatures up to 1.2 °C (Gebrechorkos *et al.* 2019). The Gidabo watershed exhibits statistically significant increases in minimum temperature across all seasons and future scenarios, with strong warming signals ($Z = 2.8–4.7$). CMIP6 projections indicate continued warming, with mean annual maximum temperature increases between 1.1 and 3.8 °C depending on scenario and period (Alaminie *et al.* 2021), while rainfall trends remain variable and uncertain (Gashaw *et al.* 2023). This consistent rise in minimum temperatures highlights increasing climate risks and the need for adaptive management in the watershed.

4.5. Mean change

CMIP6 projections indicate that many regions, such as the Mediterranean and Sahara, will face 12–18% reductions in precipitation, while others, like parts of Asia and Central Africa, may experience increases (Babaousmail *et al.* 2022). Similarly, this study shows a decline in mean annual and wet season rainfall under both SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios. However, while the baseline period shows a decreasing trend, future periods exhibit increasing trends despite lower mean values. This suggests rainfall may rise gradually within future periods, especially in the dry season, which shows signs of recovery. These results align with studies showing that extreme precipitation patterns often follow mean changes (Bador & Alexander 2022). Thus, both mean shifts and trends should be considered in climate planning.

Additionally, despite the Mann–Kendall test indicating weakly positive but insignificant precipitation trends, the mean change analysis shows declining mean rainfall across all scenarios. This difference reflects methodological contrast: the MK test captures gradual temporal evolution, while mean change compares average values between fixed periods. Thus, early dry years in the projection period lower the mean, even though rainfall shows a slight upward tendency toward the mid-century.

Similar results have been reported elsewhere in Ethiopia. In southern Ethiopia, rainfall exhibited non-significant increasing trends alongside declining seasonal means due to high inter-annual variability (Belay *et al.* 2021). In West Harerge, rainfall showed mixed or insignificant trends despite decreasing averages (Bayable *et al.* 2021). Likewise, in the Upper Blue Nile Basin, Sen's slope values indicated minor positive trends that were insufficient to offset strong variability (Melese *et al.* 2023).

These consistencies suggest that the 'decreasing mean but increasing trend' pattern is not contradictory but reflects high rainfall variability and weak long-term recovery. Consequently, future precipitation in the Gidabo watershed may remain below the historical mean, emphasizing the need for adaptive water management to cope with variable rainfall conditions.

Consistent with global projections, this study shows stronger increases in minimum temperatures up to 30.14% under high-emission scenarios compared with maximum temperatures, which rise below 7% (Kamruzzaman *et al.* 2023). Such warming, especially at night, may impact agriculture and health. While precipitation projections are more variable, many regions, including northern and southern Africa, are expected to see declines, though some areas, like Central Africa, may experience increases (Almazroui *et al.* 2020). This study also finds declining mean precipitation despite positive future trends. Moreover, extreme heatwaves and intense rainfall events are projected to increase under higher emissions (Almazroui *et al.* 2020). These combined changes emphasize the need for adaptive strategies to address rising heat stress and water challenges.

4.6. Implications of CMIP6 climate trends to water resource management in the Gidabo watershed

The projected warming and variable precipitation trends from CMIP6 models have critical implications for water resources in the Gidabo watershed. As maximum and minimum temperatures rise, evapotranspiration is expected to increase, which will reduce soil moisture and exacerbate drought frequency, thereby threatening agricultural productivity and water supply. This is supported by studies in the Awash River Basin, Ethiopia, where higher potential evapotranspiration reduces water availability under future warming scenarios (Tadese *et al.* 2020), and by research in northeastern Brazil, where reservoir evaporation significantly diminishes water storage in semi-arid regions (Rodrigues *et al.* 2024). Moreover, increased heat extremes amplify ecosystem water limitations even without major changes in precipitation (Denissen *et al.* 2024), while findings from the Blue

Nile Basin show that extreme temperature variability disrupts hydrological processes, affecting wetland stability and groundwater systems (Mohamed & El-Mahdy 2021).

In addition, precipitation projections indicate high variability, with intense, short-term rainfall events potentially triggering floods and landslides, whereas prolonged dry spells reduce water availability, a pattern also observed in the Baro River Basin (Ebissa *et al.* 2024). Therefore, these studies collectively highlight the urgent need for adaptive water management strategies in Gidabo, including watershed rehabilitation, optimized reservoir operation, flood control, efficient irrigation, and enhanced groundwater recharge. Such measures will be vital to mitigate both drought- and flood-related risks and ensure a sustainable water supply under future climate scenarios.

5. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that the Gidabo watershed is projected to experience significant climatic changes in the coming decades. While precipitation shows no statistically significant long-term trends, its mean is projected to decline, particularly during the critical wet season, indicating greater variability and a shift toward drier conditions. In stark contrast, both maximum and minimum temperatures are projected to rise significantly across all seasons and scenarios, with minimum temperatures increasing most sharply (up to +3.62 °C, or 30%, by mid-century under SSP5-8.5).

The combination of rising temperatures leading to higher evapotranspiration and more variable precipitation will likely create hotter, more evaporative, and water-stressed conditions. This intensifies the risks of agricultural droughts, ecosystem stress, and altered hydrological cycles.

Therefore, integrating these CMIP6-based climate projections into water resource planning is urgent. Prioritizing climate-resilient strategies, such as improved irrigation scheduling, watershed management, and adaptive water allocation, is essential to ensure sustainable water resource use in the Gidabo watershed and similar climate-vulnerable regions of East Africa. These findings underscore the importance of integrating climate projections into watershed management planning, particularly in developing adaptive water allocation strategies, reservoir operation rules, and soil–water conservation measures to enhance resilience in the Gidabo watershed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We extend our gratitude to the Ethiopian Meteorological Institution, which provided us with relevant information on the Gidabo watershed. Moreover, we used AI-based tools for grammar and language refinement. The authors are fully responsible for the content and conclusions.

FUNDING

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

ETHICS STATEMENT

This study did not involve any human participants, animals, or sensitive personal data, and therefore did not require ethical approval from an institutional review board. All data used in this research were obtained from publicly available sources, and the study was conducted under recognized ethical standards for scientific research.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data cannot be made publicly available; readers should contact the corresponding author for details.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare there is no conflict.

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First received 17 July 2025; accepted in revised form 11 November 2025. Available online 1 December 2025